

On a Test of the Rival Theories of Active Nitrogen.

By B. D. CHHABRA AND H. R. LUTHRA.

The excitation of the so-called forbidden lines has of late aroused considerable interest. Success in such experiments has however been rare with atoms of low atomic weight. The experiments described in the following pages were undertaken to obtain the forbidden lines of sulphur. The arguments which justified the procedure adopted in this investigation may be briefly described as follows: When a condensed electric discharge is passed through nitrogen streaming in a tube, the gases which come out continue to glow with a golden yellow colour (Lewis, *Astrophys. J.*, 1904, 20, 49). The exact nature of this after-glow (also called 'active nitrogen') is not even now fully understood.

Birge (*Nature*, 1924, 124, 642) assumes the existence of a metastable molecule with an energy content of about 14 volts. On collision (of the second kind) with an atom of another element it gives up its energy and the latter in turn becomes luminescent giving out its characteristic lines (Klein and Rosseland, *Zeitsch. Physik*, 1921, 4, 46).

Sponer (*Z. Physik.*, 1925, 34, 622) studied the spectrum of nitrogen and active nitrogen, and basing her arguments on the analysis of the band spectrum of nitrogen, previously carried out by Birge (*National Research Council Bulletin*, No. 57, 244) showed that the spectrum of active nitrogen consists of a few selected bands of nitrogen and that the strongest bands of active nitrogen correspond to vibrational quantum number $n=11$, of an electronic state of N_2 which he calls 'B'. Assuming that the non-polar nitrogen molecule breaks up into its constituent unexcited atoms under the action of a condensed discharge, and gives rise to the phenomenon of active nitrogen, we get from this hypothesis the dissociation potential of nitrogen as 11.4 volts. The long life of active nitrogen is inconsistent with the idea that the chances of the two atoms directly combining to form a molecule are very remote, for in this case the laws of conservation of energy and momentum would not be satisfied.

Some fresh light on the subject has recently been thrown by the investigations of Compton and Boyce (*Physical Rev.*, 1929, *ii*, 33, 145) on the analysis of the arc spectrum of nitrogen in the Schumann region and the excitation of the auroral green line λ 5377 by Kaplan (*Nature*, 1928, 121, 711) by a rather interesting method. Kaplan (*loc. cit.*) photographed the spectrum of active nitrogen formed from a mixture of 96 p. c. nitrogen and 4 p. c. oxygen and observed the auroral line. He explained its presence by postulating the presence of metastable atoms of nitrogen loaded to an energy of 2.37 and 3.56 volts. The presence of these metastable levels in the spectrum of nitrogen was indicated by the work of Compton and Boyce (*loc. cit.*) and Kaplan suggested that since the auroral green line was a forbidden line of oxygen atom and required about 3 volts for its excitation, it could be developed only under very special conditions. The nitrogen atoms in the after-glow which are loaded with a restricted amount of energy are very favourable for its production. This hypothesis by Kaplan (*loc. cit.*) is extremely interesting but evidently needs further experimental support.

The most stable configuration of the oxygen-like atoms gives rise to $^3P_0, 1, 2,$, 1D_2 and 1S_0 terms. The 3P terms were obtained by Hopfield (*Physical Rev.*, 1927, *ii*, 29, 924) and the singlet terms for oxygen have recently been identified by Frerichs (*Physical Rev.*, 1929, *ii*, 34, 1239) and he has conclusively shown that the auroral green line corresponds to $^1D \rightarrow ^1S$ transition.

In the course of an investigation of the spectra of selenium and tellurium, McLennan and Crawford (*Nature*, 1929, 124, 874) were able to identify the $^1D \rightarrow ^1S$ transitions for selenium and tellurium

at $7247.5 \overset{\circ}{\text{Å}}$ and $7909.2 \overset{\circ}{\text{Å}}$. (The recent work of Bowen on the spectra of nebulae makes it clear that the so-called metastable states are nothing but states of long mean life and provided that the gases involved are at sufficiently low pressure, one may expect emission of radiation corresponding to transitions between the levels ordinarily designated as metastable. In such transitions, it will be noted that the azimuthal quantum number selection rules must necessarily be violated).

The line λ $6300 \overset{\circ}{\text{Å}}$ would require for its excitation an amount of nearly the same value as in oxygen. We should therefore be able to excite this line also by the collisions of metastable nitrogen atoms in

the active nitrogen with sulphur atoms. Such an experiment, if successful, would not only enable us to locate the exact value of the metastable levels in sulphur and incidentally help us in understanding the structure of the spectrum of sulphur in the Schumann region, but would also provide a convincing test of Kaplan's theory of active nitrogen.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The apparatus employed was practically the same as used by Kichlu and Acharya (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1929, **A**, 123, 168) and in fact similar to that used by most of the investigators on this subject. The nitrogen was taken from a commercial cylinder of compressed gas. It was purified from oxygen and water vapour by passing it over sticks of yellow phosphorus and through tubes containing calcium chloride and phosphorus pentoxide.

FIG. 1.

The form of the discharge tube used is shown in Fig. 1. A condensed discharge was passed between the electrodes e_1 and e_2 . The direction in which the gas flows is indicated by arrow-heads. The active nitrogen was developed in the tube and was easily recognised by its golden yellow colour. The tube S contained powdered sulphur, which was heated to its boiling point by passing a suitable current through a nichrome wire coil surrounding the tube S. The tube G was also heated similarly to maintain the sulphur in vaporous state, thus ensuring the complete interaction of active nitrogen and sulphur vapour. The position of the slit of the spectrometer is also shown in the figure. The spectrometer

used was "higher constant deviation glass-prism spectrometer" and Ilford special rapid panchromatic plates were used for photography in the region.

Results.

When there was no sulphur in the tube S, the active nitrogen filled the tube G entirely with a golden yellow glow. When, however, sulphur was heated, the tube G was filled with a faint bluish glow, and active nitrogen was faintly visible only in the bend of the discharge tube. The photographs of the spectrum of the bluish

glow mentioned above do not show the line $\lambda 6300\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$ which is to be expected on Kaplan's theory of active nitrogen. It is possible that the forbidden lines of sulphur are not so easily excited by this method as those of oxygen, although the two are in the same group. We are led to think that Kaplan's postulate regarding the nature of active nitrogen requires further experimental support for its acceptance.

We are very thankful to Professor J. B. Seth and Dr. P. K. Kichlu for the keen interest they have been taking in the experiments described in this paper.

DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS,
GOVERNMENT COLLEGE,
LAHORE.

Received June 25, 1931.